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ABSTRACT BOOK

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EXPERIENCES FROM H2020 SMARTWATER PROJECT: SMART AND SUSTAINABLE SOIL AND WATER MANAGEMENT IN AGRICULTURE IN BIH

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Implementation of Horizon 2020 project "Promoting SMART agricultural WATER management in Bosnia and Herzegovina" (SMARTWATER) started on 1.1.2021. The Coordinator of SMARTWATER is the University of Banja Luka Faculty of Agriculture (UNI-BL). Project consortium consists of partners from BiH, Spain, Portugal and Italy. The main objective of SMARTWATER is to reinforce networking, research and S&T cooperation capacities of the University of Banja Luka (UNI-BL), the University of Sarajevo (UNSA) and other connected national institutions, in the field of sustainable agricultural water management and to increase their competency and fund-raising skills for a successful participation in the European Union Research Programs. The basic project scientific themes include: 1) cloud-based smart technologies, 2) new generation of satellite remote sensing data, 3) water-energy-food nexus and 4) climate change impact on agriculture. As part of WP3, a 3-year joint experimental studies on maize (*Zea mays* L.) at two locations in BiH and with different irrigation and fertilization regimes were also performed. With data from these experiments, several academic papers were already published open access in international Journals . Project teams promoted SMARTWATER at 20+ international conferences in BiH and abroad. In period 2021-2023 project consortium organized 3 advanced training courses, 3 summer schools, 3-year experiments, 2 stakeholders' meetings (roundtables), 3 MSc courses, 10 mutual staff exchanges, 3 R&I hands-on workshops and many more. Posts about our activities are published at social media profiles (Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn) and the SMARTWATER website . SMARTWATER project officially ends in June 2024. Twinning activities in 2024 (academic exchanges, dissemination etc.) will be aimed at promoting smart management of agricultural resources, upgrade of networking and research between partner institutions and work with project stakeholders. We ask all interested actors to visit our sites, to attend our events and to join the SMARTWATER network.

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